

Zero PM

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

Grant Agreement No. 101036756

Deliverable 7.3

September 2023

Passive sampling tool for sampling PM substances in a range of matrices

Work Package 7 – Technical Solutions, Method Development and Analysis

Deliverable Work Package Leader:
NIVA Norwegian Institute for Water Research

Revision: 0
Dissemination level: Public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036756.

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The present document has not yet received final approval from the European Commission and may be subject to changes.

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Project information

Project period:	01.10.2021 – 30.09.2026
Duration (no. of months):	17
Web-site:	www.zeropm.eu
Project coordinator:	Norwegian Geotechnical Institute, (NGI project no.: 20210423)

Project partners:

Summary

The European research project ZeroPM – “Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances” combines three interlinked strategies to tackle pollution with persistent and mobile (PM) substances: **Prevent**, **Prioritize** and **Remove**. Work Package 7 – “Technical Solutions, Method Development and Analysis” (WP7) is dedicated to the removal of PM substances. Among other things, WP7 will develop innovative monitoring and treatment methods for PM substances in drinking and waste waters. Part of this work package focuses on developing passive sampling methods for the monitoring of PM substances in various aqueous matrices and for the evaluation of drinking and wastewater treatment efficiency. Prior to their application and use under field conditions, the performance of passive samplers for the sampling of PM substances of interest needs to be established.

In this Deliverable 7.2, we report on the calibration of a versatile passive sampler for selected PM substances in water. The work initially involved calibrating the individual components of the passive sampler (i.e. the receiving phase or sorbent, and the membrane). In a second step, a full calibration study was set up and conducted in the laboratory in order to measure sampling rates for benzotriazoles, short-chain PFAS and triazine compounds with this new sampler configuration.

Batch sorbent-water sorption experiments were conducted to assess the sorption capacity of a commercially available solid phase extraction disc (Affinisep’s HLB disc) for benzotriazole and the triazine atrazine. The sorbent in a disc format had slightly lower capacity than the loose sorbent but sufficiently high capacity for use in our device. Contaminant diffusion across two microporous stainless steel mesh membranes was evaluated in a set of diffusion cell experiments. While contaminant mass transfer coefficients for the membrane with the widest pore size were too high for use in a passive sampler, those obtained with the smallest pore size membrane were deemed suitable and therefore included in two first passive sampler configurations for testing with full scale calibration study. This calibration experiment confirmed the potential of these passive sampler configurations to sample PM substances from aqueous environments. Some discrepancies between the sampling rates obtained and those estimated from diffusion cell experiment were observed and tentatively explained. Further development work is proposed and planned.

Initial testing of active air/gas sampling was conducted with two types of cartridges. One of the two types of cartridges was used to sample gas from the hydrothermal carbonisation experiments conducted at the University of the Aegean (results pending) and is presented in a separate chapter.

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Table of abbreviations	
ABN	EVOLUTE® EXPRESS ABN modified PS-DVB polymeric SPE phase for extraction of acidic, basic and neutral analytes
ATZ	Atrazine
BTZ	Benzotriazole
DGT/o-DGT	Diffusive gradients in thin films
G-TIP	Gradient time integrative passive sampler
HLB	Hydrophilic and lipophilic balance sorbent
MCX	Mixed-mode cation exchange
MPT	Microporous polyethylene tube
OH-BT	2-hydroxybenzothiazole
PAHs	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PES	Polyethersulfone
PFAS	Per and poly-fluoroalkyl substances
PM	Persistent and mobile chemicals
POCIS	Polar organic chemical integrative sampler
PRCs	Performance reference compounds
SPE	Solid phase extraction
QAQC	Quality assurance and quality control
WAX	Weak anion exchange
XAD	Amberlite® XAD®-2 styrene-divinylbenzene resin
XTR	5,6-dimethyl benzotriazole
5Me-BTZ	5-methylbenzotriazole
5Cl-BTZ	5-chlorobenzotriazole

1 Introduction

ZeroPM, which stands for Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances, is a 5 year long European research project funded under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. ZeroPM will interlink and synergize three strategies to protect the environment and human health from persistent and mobile (PM) substances: **Prevent**, **Prioritize** and **Remove**. To do this, ZeroPM will develop an evidence-based multilevel framework. The framework will guide policy, technological and market incentives to minimize use, emissions and pollution of entire groups of PM substances.

Work Package 7 – “Technical Solutions, Method Development and Analysis” (WP7) has the overall objective to demonstrate how and if legacy and prioritized PM substance pollution can be remediated. WP7 investigates innovative treatment and monitoring methods for water (ground, surface, bank filtrate, waste) and sludge to protect water resources, provide safe drinking water and protect human health and the environment, with a focus on PM substances and media from three different test sites.

Passive sampling is an effective technique used to monitor the presence and concentration of contaminants in aquatic environments. Unlike traditional grab sampling methods, passive sampling involves the deployment of devices that accumulate contaminants over a defined period, providing a more accurate representation of time-weighted average concentrations (Vrana et al., 2005). Passive sampling has been used to measure contaminant concentrations in the sea as well as in freshwater environments including groundwater (Alvarez et al., 2005; Martínez Bueno et al., 2016). Applications of passive samplers to wastewater environment and drinking water have also taken place (Clokey et al., 2023; Gobelius et al., 2019; Schulze et al., 2021). Passive samplers are generally suited to the measurement of ambient levels of contaminants in water but can also target the low levels of contaminants that can be found in remote locations. Passive sampling devices are ideally suited to the evaluation of remediation efficiency, i.e. before and after water or sediment treatment processes. Passive sampling has been applied to the evaluation of sediment remediation efficiency such as when using capping (Eek et al., 2010; Oen et al., 2011) or the treatment/removal efficiency in drinking water treatment plants (Gobelius et al., 2019). Passive sampling can be used to assess the impact from effluent release into the environment (e.g. upstream and downstream an wastewater effluent release point in a riverine environment) particularly when concentrations are likely to vary in time or to track pollution sources (Estoppey et al., 2015; Lombard et al., 2023).

While much research has been conducted to develop passive sampling devices for a wide range of chemicals, passive sampling targeting PM substances is relatively less advanced. In order for a passive sampling device to be used reliably, its performance needs to be evaluated to understand the uptake of chemicals into the sampler and assess the impact of environmental factors on this uptake. To this end, calibration experiments are conducted to determine sampling rates, R_s and evaluate how this R_s is impacted by environmental factors such as water turbulences, temperature, and presence of organic matter in the water or biofouling on the sampler's surface.

ZeroPM aims to develop the passive sampling tools necessary for the measurement of ambient levels of PM substances in water and to enable the assessment of the efficiency of drinking water and wastewater treatment at the pilot scale. This deliverable focuses therefore on the calibration of passive sampling devices for PM substances in water and reports preliminary testing of an active air/gas sampling for PM substances.

2 Task definition

Task 7.1 aims at obtaining an innovative passive sampling strategy targeting PM substances including benzotriazoles, long chain PFAS ($\geq C6$), short chain PFAS ($\leq C5$) and triazines. Passive sampling devices are to enable time-integrated sampling of PM substances in water and to assess pilot and full-scale drinking water and wastewater treatment technologies.

In order to uniformise the sampling at different sites under different hydrodynamic conditions, a polar organic chemical integrative sampler (POCIS) device was developed to ensure the uptake into the device was independent of water turbulences around the sampler.

Components of the sampler, including a receiving phase to accumulate chemicals of interest and a membrane to control the uptake have been assembled into a device which was subsequently tested in full scale passive sampling calibration experiment. This versatile tool enables the sampling of different aquatic environments and to assess drinking water treatment processes (Tasks 7.2 and 7.3) and wastewater treatment processes (Task 7.4).

In addition, part of this task is to develop an air/gas monitoring technique with solid-phase extraction cartridges that should be tested for further application in Task 7.4 to evaluate PM substance emissions with gases during sludge treatment.

3 Passive sampling tools for PM substances in water matrices

3.1 Background and introduction

3.1.1 Theory and principles of passive sampling in water

Passive sampling in water monitoring is an innovative and effective technique used to assess the presence and concentration of various contaminants in aquatic environments. Unlike traditional grab sampling methods, passive sampling involves the deployment of devices that accumulate contaminants over a defined period, providing a more accurate representation of long-term exposure levels (Vrana et al., 2005).

The theoretical basis for passive sampling in water is rooted in the principles of diffusion and equilibrium. When contaminants are present in water, they naturally tend to move

from areas of higher concentration to areas of lower concentration, driven by the process of diffusion. Passive sampling devices, made of one or more materials with an affinity for specific contaminants, are designed to exploit this process to accumulate contaminants over time.

The sampling devices contain a sorbent material with a high affinity for the compounds of interest and this retains them from the surrounding water. When exposed to water, contaminants diffuse through one or more layers or membranes into the sorbent, initially free of contaminants, until an equilibrium is reached, where the concentration of contaminants in the sorbent is proportional to the concentration in the water. This equilibrium condition allows for accurate estimation of contaminant concentrations over extended periods.

The rate of diffusion, uptake and the capacity of the sorbent material influence the sampling rate and sensitivity of the device. Factors such as temperature, water flow rate, and the properties of the contaminants also play a role in determining how efficiently passive sampling operates.

Overall, the theoretical basis of passive sampling leverages the fundamental principles of diffusion and equilibrium to capture a representative snapshot of contaminant levels in water over time, offering a more comprehensive understanding of environmental conditions compared to traditional grab sampling methods.

While passive sampling of nonpolar and non-ionised contaminants has progressed much over the last two decades (Booij et al., 2016), passive sampling of polar, mobile and persistent chemicals has been the subject of relatively less development. Different versions of the polar organic chemical integrative sampler (POCIS) have been calibrated in the laboratory or in the field and used in field application. The device in its most conventional configuration is made of loose OASIS HLB sorbent (commonly used because its relatively high affinity for polar and often mobile substances) sandwiched between two polyether sulfone membrane (PES). However, the understanding of processes that control the uptake remains relatively poorly understood. Despite much effort, the uncertainty linked to the selection and application of a sampling rate or equivalent volume of water extracted per unit of time (R_s , $L d^{-1}$) to estimate an average concentration in water for the period of exposure remains relatively high. The interaction of certain chemicals with the PES membrane (through sorption) also affects the uptake. Finally, sampling rates are relatively sensitive to water turbulences around the sampler. Higher turbulences result in a smaller diffusive boundary layer at the surface of the water and higher R_s . Conversely, stagnant conditions will increase the thickness of this boundary layer and tend to reduce R_s . For absorption based passive samplers, this has been addressed through the use of performance reference compounds (PRCs), synthetic chemicals spiked into the samplers and that will dissipate from the samplers during exposure and inform on the water-sampler exchange kinetics. However, such an approach cannot be used with adsorption-based samplers. In order to circumvent this issue and use reliable sampling rates, sampler design for polar and mobile substances has focussed on making the uptake kinetics as independent as possible from the level of turbulences in water. This can be achieved by selecting and modifying membranes to

slow the uptake. In other words, kinetics of mass transfer across the membrane needs to be low enough to control the overall uptake kinetics into the sampler. This can be obtained by increasing the thickness of the membrane or selecting a membrane material that is less permeable for the chemicals of interest. This is the working principle of samplers such as the diffusive gradient in thin film (DGT) device making use of relatively thick layers of polyacrylamide or agarose hydrogels or of the MPT sampler with a microporous polyethylene membrane. In the latter, contaminants diffuse from the water into the micropores of the PE membrane.

The resistance to mass transfer into a passive sampling device is the sum of resistances of transfer across the diffusive boundary layer at the surface of the sampler, mass transfer across (and interaction with) the membrane and diffusion and sorption to the sorbent matrix (Figure 3.1-1). SPE sorbent phases can be loose sorbent as used in the original version of POCIS (Alvarez et al., 2004) but can also be packed into discs (e.g. OASIS/Atlantic™ HLB or Affinisep’s HLB disc). However, in these conditions, the disc material or matrix will also have its own resistance to mass transfer.

Figure 3.1-1: Principle of the uptake of chemical into an adsorption base passive sampling device

The overall mass transfer resistance to the uptake into a sampler can be decomposed into the sum of mass transfer resistances in each compartment, i.e. the diffusive boundary layer ($1/k_w$), the membrane ($1/(K_{mw}k_m)$) and the sorbent phase ($1/(K_{sw}k_s)$) (Booij et al., 2017):

$$\frac{1}{k_o} = \frac{1}{k_w} + \frac{1}{K_{mw}k_m} + \frac{1}{K_{sw}k_s}$$

Eq. 3.1-1

with k_w , k_m and k_s the mass transfer coefficients for the boundary layer, the membrane and the sorbent phase, respectively, and K_{mw} and K_{sw} the membrane-water and sorbent phase-water sorption coefficients, respectively.

For a sampler's R_s to be insensitive to the level of water turbulences (i.e. with $1/k_o = \text{constant}$), the term $1/k_w$ needs to be negligible in comparison with the other terms.

Considering $R_s = Ak_o$, with A the sampling surface area, the equation above can be re-written as:

$$\frac{1}{R_{s(in\ situ)}} = \frac{1}{R_{s,max}} + \frac{1}{Ak_w}$$

Eq. 3.1-2

With $R_{s,max}$ the maximum R_s that can be achieved when mass transfer resistance in the boundary layer is negligible.

Performance criteria when designing a passive sampler:

- Appropriate time window for integrative monitoring
- Sampling rate, R_s , that are insensitive to the level of water turbulences experienced during in situ exposures in water
- High affinity and selectivity for analytes of interest
- Adequate sensitivity, limits of detection/quantification

The time window for integrative monitoring can be adapted by modifying the surface area to sorption capacity ratio of the sampler.

Sampling rates independent of water turbulences around the sampler can be achieved by selecting a membrane with relatively low(er) permeability for the analytes of interest or a thick(er) membrane layer.

The selection of an adequate type of and amount of sorption material contributes to high sorption capacity and lower limits of detection. Sampler selectivity can be improved by selecting an appropriate combination of sorption phase and membrane type.

Ultimately, a single device configuration will not enable passive sampling of all PM substances of interest. Instead, different configurations are required to target different types or classes of PM substances.

3.1.2 Passive samplers used for polar and ionised substances

Different devices have been developed in the last few years to passive sample polar and ionised substances, including PM compounds (Figure 3.1-2). DGT and gradient time integrative passive sampler (G-TIP) devices rely on a relatively small sampling window (a few cm^2) compared with POCIS or MPT samplers. Since the overall R_s is proportional to the surface area, these devices will exhibit the lowest R_s . Low sampling rates can in turn affect limits of detection. Depending on the capacity of the receiving phase, the magnitude of the R_s will also dictate how long the uptake of certain chemicals into the sampler can remain in the integrative phase of uptake. For example, a sampler with high R_s and low receiving phase capacity will equilibrate faster than a sampler with low R_s and large capacity for the chemical of interest.

MPT, DGT and G-TIP samplers have been designed to be insensitive to water turbulences during deployment by using relatively thick cylindrical microporous polyethylene membrane for the MPT sampler or an agarose or polyacrylamide hydrogel layer for the DGT device (Fauvelle et al., 2017; Verhagen et al., 2020). The R_s for these devices are generally in the range of 1-10 mL d⁻¹. A different device has also been tested for the sampling of PFAS compounds also based on diffusion across an agarose layer but with a larger sampling surface area to try and increase R_s of DGT (Urík et al., 2020). Values of R_s reported with POCIS using a PES membrane are significantly higher and generally in the range of 100-300 mL d⁻¹ (Booij and Chen, 2018). These can be even higher when using nylon mesh as membrane (Belles et al., 2014; Hale et al., 2021). However, the uptake of chemicals into POCIS is most likely partly controlled by transfer across the boundary layer at the surface of the sampler resulting in R_s that will vary with level of turbulences in the water surrounding the sampler. The G-TIP sampler is particularly interesting when working with substances with no affinity to simple, commercially available SPE sorbents. The receiving phase is water that slowly equilibrates with water outside the sampler. The original version of POCIS made use of loose SPE sorbent which resulted in a very heterogenous distribution of the sorbent sandwiched between two PES membranes. The reproducibility of measurements may be superior with devices such as DGT or the Chemcatcher where the sorbent is either stabilised in an agarose gel layer or a 47 mm SPE disc, respectively.

Figure 3.1-2: Different passive sampling devices that have been applied for the sampling of polar and ionised substances in water.

3.1.3 Passive sampling for ZeroPM PM substances

For PFAS passive sampling, POCIS has been used with Oasis HLB or WAX sorbents (Gobelius et al., 2019; Kaserzon et al., 2014), Strata XAW sorbent (Atoufi and Lampert; Kaserzon et al., 2019) and a combination of both Oasis WAX and Fluoroflash® sorbents (Atoufi and Lampert; Hale et al., 2021) (Table 3.1-1). These sorbents have been used with either a nylon or PES membrane. Higher R_s for short-chain perfluoroalkyl carboxylates with a C3-C6 perfluorocarbon chain lengths and perfluorobutane sulfonate (PFBS) were obtained for POCIS with WAX sorbent than those prepared with HLB sorbent (Gobelius et al., 2019). Interaction of certain chemicals with the PES membrane through sorption renders the understanding of the uptake and prediction of sampling rate more difficult. Such membrane sorption can result in a lag phase in the accumulation of the chemical in the receiving phase. Using 10 µm-nylon mesh allowed the accumulation of a broad range of PFAS compounds with no observable interaction with the membrane (Hale et al., 2021).

For melamine, atrazine and other triazines, a version of the DGT sampler composed of a mixed-mode SPE sorbent MCX cast in a gel and agarose-polyacrylamide diffusive gel covered with a nylon filter (Liu et al., 2021) was tested. Linear accumulation from a 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ solution was checked over 6 days. Melamine masses accumulated indicated a R_s just under 10 mL d^{-1} .

An adapted version of POCIS and Chemcatcher was made from an SDB disk behind a protective PES membrane for sampling a range of relatively polar substances (Reymond et al., 2023). These included selected benzotriazoles and atrazine. Maximum sampling rates obtained with this version of the sampler were in the range of 50-100 mL d^{-1} .

Table 3.1-1: Existing passive sampling devices that have been subject to some previous testing in water.

Sampler type	Membrane	Sorbent	Sampling (mL d^{-1})	Compounds
DGT	Agarose-polyacrylamide hydrogels	OASIS HLB, MCX, WAX	5-10	PFAS, melamine
POCIS	Polyethersulfone membrane	SDB disk, HLB and WAX powdered sorbent	50-300	Benzotriazoles
MPT	Microporous polyethylene	HLB and WAX Powdered sorbent (or equivalents)	10-20	PFAS ++
G-TIP	Microporous polyethylene	Water	~ few mL	Very polar substances

3.1.4 Passive sampler calibration in the laboratory

Membrane calibration

Different procedures are available for the study of transfer of chemicals through porous and semipermeable membranes.

A diffusion cell experiment can be used to study the movement of substances across a semipermeable or microporous membrane. The setup typically consists of two compartments separated by the membrane under study. Setting up the diffusion cell involves preparing two compartments: one on each side of the membrane creating a gradient of concentration between a donor compartment containing water spiked with chemicals of interest and an acceptor compartment initially free of these chemicals. The system is agitated to minimise the impact of the diffusive boundary layer on transfer kinetics across the membrane. As the experiment progresses, substances in the donor compartment move through the membrane into the receiver compartment principally through diffusion across the membrane. The experiment is complete when both compartments reach equilibrium and the same concentration level. Concentrations of the chemicals of interest are measured in both donor and acceptor compartment during the

experiment. Ultimately the data are interpreted by estimating a diffusion coefficient for the membrane material. Such a system is generally suitable for chemicals that do not appreciably sorb to the membrane. Experiments may be conducted at different water turbulence levels in order to evaluate the effect of the boundary layer on the overall mass transfer across the membrane being tested.

For the data interpretation, diffusion across the membrane can be estimated from the changes in concentration of chemicals in the donor and acceptor phases of the diffusion cell, under the assumption that sorption into the membrane is negligible. In our case, diffusion is in water in the pores of the stainless-steel mesh.

$$D_{SS} = \frac{1}{\beta t} \ln\left(\frac{C_{D,0} - C_{A,0}}{C_{D,t} - C_{A,t}}\right)$$

Eq. 3.1-3

With D_{SS} the apparent diffusion coefficient in the mesh, $C_{D,0}$ and $C_{A,0}$ the initial concentrations in donor and acceptor phases, $C_{D,t}$ and $C_{A,t}$ concentrations at time = t .

The term β can be estimated from:

$$\beta = \left(\frac{A}{\delta}\right)\left(\frac{1}{V_D} + \frac{1}{V_A}\right)$$

Eq. 3.1-4

With A the surface area of exchange between donor and acceptor containers, δ the thickness of the membrane and V_A and V_D the volumes of the acceptor and donor phases. The interpretation of the results from diffusion cell experiments are based on establishing the slope of the regression of $\ln\left(\frac{C_{D,0} - C_{A,0}}{C_{D,t} - C_{A,t}}\right)$ against time (t). From this, D_{SS} can be estimated together with the mass transfer coefficient across the membrane and diffusion coefficients for the chemicals of interest in water since no interaction with the membrane is expected and transport is expected through diffusion in water in the pores of the stainless steel.

Another type of experiment that can be undertaken to investigate transport of chemicals in films or membranes include film stack experiments. In a film stack experiment, different films with same or varying characteristics are chosen for the experiment and stacked together in a controlled manner, creating a layered structure. Two options are available for spiking chemicals of interest in the film stack: either a side of the film stack is exposed to a solution spiked with these chemicals or alternatively chemicals are directly loaded into one of the layers of the stack. Chemicals are then left to diffuse across the layers. The diffusion profile can then be modelled in order to estimate a diffusion coefficient for the material. Such experiments have been conducted to investigate diffusion of PFAS and other chemicals in agarose gel (Bonnaud et al., 2021; Urik et al., 2020) or hydrophobic pollutants in LDPE or silicone rubber (Pintado-Herrera et al., 2016; Rusina et al., 2010; Valderrama et al., 2016).

Affinity and sorption capacity of receiving phases

Batch experiments can be conducted in the laboratory to assess the sorption capacity of different sorbents materials to be used in passive sampling devices (Bäuerlein et al., 2012; Ghorbani Gorji et al., 2023; Huysman et al., 2019). These tests aim to estimate sorbent-water distribution or partition coefficients (K_d or K_p expressed in $L\ kg^{-1}$):

$$K_d = \frac{C_s}{C_w}$$

Eq. 3.1-5

Ideally, K_d should be obtained by measuring the concentration of the chemical of interest on the sorbent and in the water at the end of the batch experiment.

Batch sorption experiment can be undertaken to estimate distribution coefficients, investigate modes of sorption of chemicals to different types of sorbents and chemical groups on the sorbents, or study the impact of pH, salinity or temperature. Sorption isotherm experiments generally investigate the impact of concentration level on sorption. While procedures for the evaluation of sorption of neutral and hydrophobic compounds absorption into polymeric materials are relatively well established (Booij et al., 2017), those involving hydrophilic and sometimes ionised chemicals relying on adsorption processes are less formalised.

Full scale calibration studies

Full scale calibrations are generally conducted in the laboratory to evaluate the sampling rates of one or more devices or to investigate how certain factors such as temperature, water turbulences or fouling can affect these sampling rates. Passive sampling devices are exposed under controlled conditions to measured/known water concentrations over a certain period of time. The amount of chemical accumulated in the sampler is measured by successively removing samplers from the water over time. The exposure concentration is measured regularly. The sampling rate, R_s ($L\ d^{-1}$) is calculated from the mass of chemicals, m_{acc} (ng) and the concentration in water for the period of exposure (C_w or C_{free} in $ng\ L^{-1}$):

$$R_s = \frac{m_{acc}}{C_w t}$$

Eq. 3.1-6

Conducting a calibration experiment for expected field exposures can help verify any possible deviation from linear uptake towards the end of the exposure resulting from reaching pseudo-equilibrium/saturation conditions. A deviation from linear uptake can also result from a gradual increase in mass transfer resistance in of the compartments of a passive sampler.

To take into account this possibility of reaching pseudo-equilibrium, a full equation can also be used to estimate C_w :

$$C_w = \frac{m_{ACC}}{mK_d \left(1 - e^{\frac{-R_s t}{K_d m}}\right)}$$

Eq. 3.1-7

These equations can be used to estimate R_s from calibration experiments where m_{ACC} and C_w are measured over time during the course of the experiment. In the modelling of uptake and determination of R_s , K_d can either be considered as an unknown and be optimised together with R_s or can be taken from literature or measurements (e.g. from the sorbent-water distribution obtained through batch studies).

3.2 Experimental

3.2.1 Sorbent evaluation

Batch equilibrium tests were conducted with four benzotriazoles (benzotriazole (BTZ), 5-methylbenzotriazole (5Me-BTZ), 5-chlorobenzotriazole (5Cl-BTZ), 5,6-dimethyl benzotriazole (XTR)), 2-hydroxybenzothiazole (OH-BT) and atrazine (ATZ)). A comparison between the Affinisep HLB disc and loose HLB sorbent was investigated. Loose HLB sorbent was weighed (80 ± 0.1 mg) into a 50 mL polypropylene centrifuge tube in triplicate, which represented an equal mass of sorbent in one quarter of the HLB disc, taking into consideration the disc composition of 90:10% sorbent:binder ratio. One HLB disc was quartered, and each weighed (80 ± 1 mg) into a 50 mL centrifuge tube, in triplicate. For quality control and quality assurance (QAQC), one blank of loose sorbent, one blank disc and one tube with no sorbent or disc was also included. All samples and QAQC were preconditioned with 5 mL methanol and gently shaken for 30 mins before centrifugation at 2500 rpm for 5 mins. The supernatant was then decanted. The preconditioning was repeated with 5 mL ultra-pure water, twice. Spiked water containing all six analytes, 50 mL of 50 ng mL^{-1} in ultra-pure water was added to each sample, except for the three blanks where 50 mL of ultra-pure water was added. One blank tube was also spiked to ensure that no sorption onto the tubes was observed throughout the experiment. After spiking samples were vortexed and centrifuged before an aliquot of 0.2 mL was taken for establishing initial concentrations, $t=0$, which was taken approximately 10 minutes after spiking. All samples were then placed on a side-to-side shaker at 120 rpm and subsequent aliquots of 0.2 mL were taken at 1, 2, 4, 8 and 24 hours after 5 mins of centrifugation at 2500 rpm and placed in a analysis vial. Samples were spiked with internal standard mixture (0.01 mL of 100 ng mL^{-1} d6-5-methylbenzotriazole and d5-atrazine) and placed in the fridge until analysis.

The HLB sorbent and discs were extracted using slightly different methods as follows. The disc and the spiked water were separated and the disc gently dried using clean paper towel to remove any remaining droplets of water. The disc was then placed into a 15 ml centrifuge tube with 0.05 mL of internal standard ($20 \text{ } \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ mix). After 30 mins the 5 mL of 0.1% formic acid in methanol:acetonitrile (1:1,v:v) and sonicated for 30 mins before the supernatant was transferred into a new tube. The solvent extraction was

repeated with a further 5 mL of 0.1% formic acid in methanol:acetonitrile. Extracts were then diluted 20 times using ultrapure water before analysis.

The HLB sorbent samples were passed through a rinsed empty solid phase extraction (SPE) cartridge (SPE) with a frit to separate the water and the sorbent phases. The SPE cartridge was rinsed with 5 mL of methanol, and 5 mL of ultrapure water twice. The tubes containing the sorbent were rinsed with 1 mL of ultrapure water to ensure all sorbent was collected on the SPE cartridge. The cartridges were then dried before 0.05 mL of internal standard (20 µg/mL mix) was added. After 30 mins the sorbent was eluted with 2 x 5 mL of 0.1% formic acid in methanol:acetonitrile. Extracts were then diluted 20 times using ultrapure water before analysis.

Analysis of the benzotriazoles was carried out using ultra performance liquid chromatography system coupled to triple quadrupole mass spectrometry system (Acquity UPLC, Waters and Xevo TQ-S, Waters). Detailed information on the analysis can be found in Appendix.

K_d values were calculated using the average measured sorbent or disc concentration (C_s), divided by the average measured final water concentration (C_w). The K_d values were log transformed to normalise variances.

$$\log K_d = \text{Log} \left(\frac{C_s}{C_w} \right)$$

Eq. 3.2-1

Single factor ANOVA using Microsoft Excel software was used to identify significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between the HLB sorbent and the HLB disc for each analyte.

3.2.2 Membrane calibration

A diffusion cell experiment was carried out to estimate the mass transfer coefficient across selected membranes. These were made of stainless steel with porosities of 5 µm and 10 µm, respectively (Table 3.2-1). The membranes were sandwiched between two cells with approximately 120 mL of ultrapure water on each side (Figure 3.2-1). One side of the diffusion cell was spiked with 50 ng mL⁻¹ of a mixture of four benzotriazoles (BTZ, 5Me-BTZ, 5Cl-BTZ and XTR), OH-BT and ATZ. The diffusion cells were placed perpendicular on a side-to-side shaker (150 rpm, 5 cm amplitude) for several days in a controlled temperature room of 20 °C. Aliquots of 1 mL were taken at 10 time points from each side of the diffusion cell. Before analysis, internal standard mixture was added (0.01 mL of 100 ng mL⁻¹ d₆-5-methylbenzotriazole and d₅-atrazine).

Figure 3.2-1: Diffusion cell experiments set up on a horizontal shaker.

In the current diffusion cell system, V_D and V_A were the same and equal to 125 mL, the surface area of the opening with a diameter of 3.4 cm between acceptor and donor compartment was 9.08 cm^2 . Considering a mesh thickness for the stainless steel of 0.02 cm, β is equal to 7.26 cm^2 .

Table 3.2-1: Main characteristics of the two types of membranes tested.

Membrane	Stainless steel	Stainless steel
Pore size (μm)	5	10
Thickness (mm)	0.2	0.2
Pore (% vol/vol)	12	51
Mass (g cm^{-2})	0.069	0.057

Validation of boundary layer thickness conditions in diffusion cell experiments are generally obtained through testing multiple levels of water turbulences or ignored when transport through the membrane is sufficiently slow. In our case, an experiment was conducted using the same conditions as above, but the membrane was replaced by a silicone sheet spiked with deuterated polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). Clean silicone sheets were also used in both donor and acceptor compartments to act as an infinite sink for chemicals leaching from the silicone sheet clamped between the two compartments. Diffusion cells were placed on an orbital shaker for 14 days at 150 rpm in identical conditions as those used to test stainless steel mesh membranes. The resistance to mass transfer of chemicals out of the silicone is governed by transfer across the boundary layer. This means that kinetics of dissipation of the deuterated PAHs are directly related to boundary layer conditions in the diffusion cell.

3.2.3 Full scale laboratory calibrations

Methodology

A laboratory calibration was conducted using POCIS type sampler with two configurations both using the $5 \mu\text{m}$ stainless steel membrane, with either the Affinisep HLB passive sampling disc or the Waters/Atlantic™ Oasis HLB solid-phase extraction disc. The Affinisep disc is made of 90 % sorbent and 10 % binding agent whereas the

Oasis HLB disc is loose HLB sorbent packed between glass fibre membrane (Atlantic™ disc).

The Affinisep discs were preconditioned with 20 mL of methanol and gently shaken at 75 rpm for 30 mins before decanting the methanol and further conditioning with 20 mL of ultra-pure water and gently shaken for another 30 mins. The discs were conditioned with an additional 20 mL of ultra-pure water before assembly. The HLB/Atlantic™ discs were preconditioned with methanol and then twice with ultra-pure water. The sorbent layers were sandwiched between the stainless-steel membrane and the POCIS ring, so only one side of the sorbent layers were exposed. The calibration was set-up in two 98 L stainless steel pots, linked together with a peristaltic pump. Three overhead stirrers with four POCIS holders (three POCIS per holder, thus capacity for 12 POCIS rings on each stirrer) on a rod that submerged the POCIS below the water's surface (

Figure 3.2-2). The stirrers were set to 50 rpm. A total approximate volume of 81 L of reverse osmosis water per pot (162 L combined) were spiked with an environmentally relevant, nominal, concentrations of 0.05 ng mL⁻¹ of ten different analytes (Table 3.2-2)(Janna et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2023). The contaminants spiked in the test system covered each class of chemicals from the ZeroPM list: triazines, triazoles and PFAS. Water samples of approximately 10 mL were taken daily to ensure depletion of the spiked concentration was <20%. Samplers were removed from the water (Affinisep discs, n=3, Waters, n=1) on days 1, 2, 4, 7, 14 and 28 days. Days 2 and 14 samplers (Affinisep, n=3) were repeated in the latter half of the experiment to ensure consistency of the results. Results from the first seven days of the experiment, for benzotriazoles and atrazine are presented in this report, as the experiment is ongoing.

Table 3.2-2: List of target analytes spiked into the passive sampling laboratory calibration experiment and their identifiers.

CAS Registry Number	Chemical class	Analytes	Abbreviation
1912-24-9	Triazine	Atrazine	ATZ
95-14-7	Triazole	Benzotriazole	BTZ
136-85-6	Triazole	5-methyl benzotriazole	5Me-BTZ
94-97-3	Triazole	5-chlorobenzotriazole	5Cl-BTZ
4184-79-6	Triazole	5,6-dimethyl benzotriazole	XTR
934-34-9	Triazole	2-hydroxybenzotriazole	OH-BT
335-67-1	PFAS	Perfluorooctanoic acid	PFOA
76-05-1	PFAS	Trifluoroacetic acid	TFA
422-64-0	PFAS	Perfluoropropanoic acid	PFPrA
354-88-1	PFAS	Perfluoroethanesulfonic acid	PFEtS

Figure 3.2-2: Photographs showing the laboratory calibration experiment in progress. Part A indicates where different parts of the set-up are in varying colours and Part B, shows the experimental set-up with the samplers submerged in the water in Pot 1.

Daily water samples were extracted approximately every second day, using a HLB cartridge (Oasis PRiME HLB 3 mL Vac Cartridge, 60 mg) to concentrate the samples 100 times to allow for accurate quantitation. The cartridge was preconditioned with 4 mL of methanol followed by 4 mL of ultra-pure water, twice. Internal standard mixture (0.01 mL of 100 ng mL⁻¹) was added to the 10 mL aliquot, which was then passed through the cartridge, with an attached plastic syringe reservoir. A rinse step of 1 mL of ultrapure water was used to rinse the tube, and also passed through the cartridge. The syringe was then used to pass air through and dry the cartridge before 1 mL of methanol:acetonitrile (1:1) was used to elute the cartridge into a 1.5 mL glass analysis vial. The extract was evaporated under a gentle nitrogen gas (N₂) stream to 0.1 mL. This was then transferred into a glass insert in a new 1.5 mL glass analysis vial for analysis. Therefore, samples were concentrated 100 times.

Passive sampling Affinisep discs were extracted similarly to the discs in the batch equilibrium studies. The Affinisep samplers were placed in the fridge until extraction. The POCIS rings were carefully dismantled, and the sorbent membrane was transferred into a 50 mL centrifuge tube. The same procedure was conducted for the OASIS/Atlantic™ discs, but they were also freeze-dried to ensure the loose sorbent within the disc was dry before beginning extraction. Both HLB samplers were then artificially fortified with internal standards and were left to rest for 30 mins. Next, the samplers were extracted with 7 mL of 0.1 % formic acid in methanol:acetonitrile (1:1, v/v) and placed to shake at 120 rpm for 60 mins. The solvent was decanted into a 15 mL centrifuge tube and the extraction process was repeated with a further 7 mL 0.1 % formic acid in methanol:acetonitrile (1:1, v/v). The Oasis/Atlantic™ discs were extracted with 10 + 10 mL of 0.1 % formic acid in methanol:acetonitrile as they were completely dry. One millilitre of extract was aliquoted into a LC vial for analysis.

R_s determination

Calibration data from the first 7 days of exposure were interpreted with two models, one assuming a linear uptake over the 7-day sampling period and one accounting for the possibility of reaching some pseudo equilibrium after a while. Since water concentrations in the exposure water were measured daily, a simple numerical model was set up in MS Excel to estimate R_s from m_{ACC} and C_w. A root mean square error (RMSE) of the differences in modelled and measured m_{ACC} after 1, 2, 4, and 7 days was used to estimate differences between predicted and measured accumulation curves. The optimisation of R_s or R_s and K_d was conducted with the solver add-in by minimising this RMSE.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{12} \left(\frac{|m_{Acc,1d,rep1} - m_{Acc,model 1d}|^2}{m_{Acc,1d,rep1}} + \frac{|m_{Acc,1d,rep2} - m_{Acc,model 1d}|^2}{m_{Acc,1d,rep2}} + \dots \right)}$$

Eq. 3.2-2

3.3 Results and Discussion

3.3.1 Selection of sampler configuration

The design of a passive sampler needs to be based on the expected performance of the sampler in terms of field limits of detection and integrative uptake time windows. Reported R_s for the DGT, MPT and G-TIP samplers are generally in the range of 5-10 mL d⁻¹ principally because of the sampling surface area of a few cm² (the R_s is directly proportional to A). A POCIS configuration with a surface area of ~ 40 cm² was initially selected with the objective of field limits of detection < 1 ng L⁻¹ for a few weeks exposure.

One requirement for the membrane was to use a material for which our chemicals of interest have minimal affinity for. Certain compounds have shown affinity for and sorption to PES membranes used in the standard version of the POCIS which complicates the understanding of the uptake and sometimes results in an initial lag phase in the accumulation in the receiving phase. We have identified some stainless-steel membranes with a thickness of 200 µm thickness and pore sizes of 5 and 10 µm that could be used in a passive sampling device. Mass transfer of PM substances to the receiving phase is expected to be through diffusion in water in the pores of the mesh.

Another criterion in the preparation of a passive sampling device is a relatively straightforward sourcing of materials for production. For the receiving phase, different loose sorbents or disc formats are commercially available. For benzotriazoles and selected PFAS or triazines, HLB discs (from Affinisep or OASIS/Atlantic™) may provide a suitable component for accumulation of these compounds. For other PM substances such as melamine and PFAS, OASIS MCX and WAX sorbents have previously been used.

3.3.2 Sampler calibration for benzotriazoles

Sorption of HLB and benzotriazoles.

The average log K_d values across all six analytes ranged from 3.4 to 4.5 for the loose HLB sorbent and 3.4 to 4.3 for the HLB disc. While the range is narrow and similar for both HLB types, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed between the loose sorbent and the disc for ATZ ($p < 0.002$), BTZ ($p = 0.006$) and 5Me-BTZ ($p = 0.039$).

While the log K_d values were similar between the two HLB types the rate of uptake or time to equilibrium between the two were different (Table 3.3-1 and Figure 3.3-1). The rate of uptake for the HLB sorbent was almost instantaneous, with the average concentrations of the spiking solution across all six analytes being 44.2 ± 3.8 ng mL⁻¹ and average $t=0$ concentrations, taken 10 mins after spiking, 6.1 ± 1.6 ng mL⁻¹. This high accumulation after only 10 mins is likely due to the direct contact and high surface area of the sorbent with the spiked solution. In comparison to the exposed sorbent, the rate of uptake by the HLB disc was several hours slower and had reached equilibrium by approximately 24 hours. This slower rate of accumulation by the HLB disc compared to

the loose sorbent is ideal within a passive sampling device as uptake will likely remain in a linear phase for longer. This may allow for the use of HLB disc as an equilibrium sampler for water media having more constant concentrations, like groundwater, by extending the exposure time.

Figure 3.3-1: Average concentrations \pm standard deviation ($n=3$) of water samples taken at 0, 1, 2, 4, 8, 24, 49 and 168 hours (log scale) after spiking nominal 50 ng mL^{-1} of a mixture (four benzotriazoles, 2-hydroxybenzothiazole and atrazine) in tubes containing either loose HLB sorbent (left-hand side figures) or HLB disc (right-hand side figures).

Table 3.3-1: Estimated sorbent-water and disc-water distribution coefficients (average \pm standard deviation ($n=3$)) determined in batch experiments after seven days equilibration time on a horizontal shaker at 120 rpm.

	ATZ	BTZ	5Me-BTZ	5Cl-BTZ	XTR	OH-BT
Sorbent	4.37 ± 0.22	3.57 ± 0.13	3.92 ± 0.21	4.03 ± 0.23	4.13 ± 0.20	4.19 ± 0.25
Disc	3.40 ± 0.01	3.80 ± 0.02	4.23 ± 0.03	4.20 ± 0.04	4.12 ± 0.04	4.12 ± 0.04

Benzotriazole mass transfer in the membrane

We tested the transfer of benzotriazoles and atrazine across stainless steel membrane with two porosity sizes of 5 and 10 μm to assess the changes in concentration of PM substances in donor and acceptor compartments, for each experiment. Minimal

differences can be observed for the different chemicals. Mass balances are close to 100 % and this is confirmed by the final concentration in both compartments reaching ½ of the initial donor compartment concentration (Figure 3.3-2). This is reached after 200-300 min with the 10 µm stainless steel while it took over 1200 min for these concentrations to equilibrate with the 5 µm stainless steel mesh.

Figure 3.3-2: Changes in concentration of benzotriazoles and atrazine (ng mL^{-1}) in donor (closed circles) and acceptor (open circles) compartment with time (min) during diffusion cell experiments with stainless steel mesh with 5 and 10 µm pore sizes during diffusion cell experiments conducted on a horizontal shaker at 150 rpm at 20 °C.

Donor and acceptor concentrations were used to estimate $\ln(C_{D,0}-C_{A,0})/(C_{D,t}-C_{A,t})$ for each timepoint t (Figure 3.3-3). Slopes, β_{DSS} , are clearly steeper for the 10 µm membrane than for the 5 µm one. No clear differences in transfer can be seen for the

different compounds with the 10 μm stainless steel. A slightly lower slope can be seen for atrazine with the stainless steel with smallest pore size.

Figure 3.3-3: Modelling of the change in concentration with time in donor and acceptor compartment. Note that timepoints included are only those prior to reaching equilibrium between the two compartments (hence difference x-axis scales). Slopes are equal to βD_{ss} (see text).

Regressions were estimated using Microsoft Excel and are given in the table below (Table 3.3-2). Values of βD_{ss} for the 10 μm stainless steel ranged from 0.584 for BTZ to 0.758 for OH-BT. For the 5 μm membrane, these values are substantially lower with a range of 0.106 for OH-BTZ to 0.128 for 5Me-BTZ. These values are between 4 and 7

times lower than with the membrane with higher pore size (except for atrazine). The constant β is a function of the diffusion cell set-up (volume of donor and acceptor phases, V_D and V_A , and surface area of the mass transfer window, A) and of the membrane thickness (δ). It has units of cm^{-2} and is equal to 10 cm^{-2} for both membranes. Apparent diffusion coefficients for the stainless-steel mesh were calculated from the slope of the regression and β . Since the porosity of the stainless steel membranes was estimated, the Weissberg relationship (used principally for diffusion in sediments; (Boudreau, 1996)) was used to correct for tortuosity of the mesh to estimate diffusion coefficients in water (D_w). Finally, a comparison of D_w from the experiment with that calculated with the Stokes-Einstein relationship ($D_{w, \text{Stokes-Einstein}}$) can help determine whether mass transfer data from these experiments appear to be realistic. There is no more than 20-30 % difference between $D_{w, 5 \mu\text{m}}$ and $D_{w, \text{Stokes-Einstein}}$ for all compounds (Table 3.3-2). The mass transfer of chemicals across the finer stainless-steel mesh is in line with what could be expected from diffusion coefficients of these compounds in water. Values of $D_{w, 10 \mu\text{m}}$, however, are 3-5 times higher than $D_{w, \text{Stokes-Einstein}}$. This would tend to indicate that the observed mass transfer across the mesh with higher porosity is higher than expected based on diffusion coefficients in water. It is possible that considering the higher porosity of the $10 \mu\text{m}$ stainless steel membrane that slight advection takes place and increases observed mass transfer.

Table 3.3-2: Modelling of mass transfer across the stainless-steel mesh assuming negligible effects of possible boundary layer conditions.

	ATZ	BTZ	5Me-BTZ	5Cl-BTZ	XTR	OH-BTZ
$\beta D_{SS, 10 \mu\text{m}}$ (slope, h^{-1})	0.611	0.584	0.608	0.688	0.622	0.758
R^2	0.70	0.99	0.99	0.90	1.00	0.99
$\beta D_{SS, 5 \mu\text{m}}$ (slope, h^{-1})	0.054	0.121	0.128	0.115	0.108	0.106
R^2	0.93	1.00	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.98
$D_{SS, 10 \mu\text{m}}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	1.70E-05	1.62E-05	1.69E-05	1.91E-05	1.73E-05	2.11E-05
$D_{SS, 5 \mu\text{m}}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	1.49E-06	3.37E-06	3.55E-06	3.18E-06	3.00E-06	2.95E-06
$D_{w, 10 \mu\text{m}}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	2.84E-05	2.71E-05	2.82E-05	3.20E-05	2.89E-05	3.52E-05
$D_{w, 5 \mu\text{m}}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	4.64E-06	1.05E-05	1.11E-05	9.94E-06	9.36E-06	9.21E-06
MW (g mol^{-1})	215.68	119.12	133.15	153.57	147.18	151.19
$D_{w, \text{Stokes-Einstein}}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	5.95E-06	9.07E-06	8.38E-06	7.57E-06	7.80E-06	7.65E-06
MW: Molecular weight						

With knowledge of D_{SS} and δ , it is possible to estimate mass transfer coefficients, k_m for the stainless-steel membranes from $k_m = D_{SS} / \delta$. These are reported in the table below with units of $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ principally to have numbers easier to visualise and compare (Table 3.3-3). Mass transfer coefficients for the $5 \mu\text{m}$ stainless steel membrane were in the range of 0.74 to $1.78 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ depending on the chemical. Mass transfer coefficients for the membrane with wider pore size ranged from 8.11 to 10.53. As expected from the porosities of the two membranes, the $5 \mu\text{m}$ pore size exhibits the lowest mass transfer coefficients for our PM substances and appear more suitable for our purpose.

Table 3.3-3: Mass transfer coefficients, k_m for the two stainless steel membranes assuming negligible effects of possible boundary layer conditions.

	ATZ	BTZ	5Me-BTZ	5Cl-BTZ	XTR	OH-BTZ
$k_{m-ss, 10 \mu m}$ ($\mu m s^{-1}$)	8.49	8.11	8.44	9.55	8.64	10.53
$k_{m-ss, 5 \mu m}$ ($\mu m s^{-1}$)	0.74	1.68	1.78	1.59	1.50	1.48
k_w for WBL* ($\mu m s^{-1}$)	3-18					
k_m for DGTs gel** ($\mu m s^{-1}$)	0.25-1.0					
k_m for MPT sampler*** ($\mu m s^{-1}$)	0.2-0.5					
*From data from Glanzmann et al. (2022) for water velocities of 0.05 to 0.4 m s ⁻¹						
**Calculated from contaminant diffusion coefficients of (Bonnaud et al., 2021) in DGT hydrogels and a 0.8 mm gel thickness						
***Calculated from R_s and A from (Kaserzon et al., 2019)						

The next step is to put these mass transfer coefficient values in perspective with k_m for other membranes or mass transfer coefficients for the boundary layer, k_w forming at the surface of the sampler during deployment. Glanzmann et al. (2022) found that under laminar flow in channels, k_w values ranged from 3 to 18 $\mu m s^{-1}$ for water velocities in the range of 0.05 to 0.4 m s⁻¹. Considering diffusion coefficients of chemicals in agarose or polyacrylamide hydrogels in the range of 2-7 $10^{-6} cm^2 s^{-1}$, and gel thicknesses of 0.8 mm, k_m values in the range of 0.25-1 $\mu m s^{-1}$ can be expected for hydrogel membranes of DGT (Bonnaud et al., 2021). Values of k_m for the 5 μm -pore size membrane tested here are slightly higher than that. What this means is that DGT, owing to the lower mass transfer coefficient (higher resistance to mass transfer), may be a little more insensitive to water turbulences than a device based on the 5 μm stainless steel membrane.

The sampling rate R_s of a passive sampler can be estimated from the product of the sampling surface area, A and the overall mass transfer coefficient, k_o . In the case of a passive sampling device relying on a 5 μm stainless steel membrane to control the kinetics of uptake (i.e. assuming $k_o = k_m$), $R_s = A k_{m-ss, 5\mu m}$. Considering the total sampling surface of POCIS of $\sim 40 cm^2$, R_{s-max} can be expected to be in the range of 257-582 mL d⁻¹ (Table 3.3-4).

Table 3.3-4: Predicted R_{s-max} values for device such as POCIS with a 40 cm² sampling surface and equipped with a 5 μm stainless steel membrane.

	ATZ	BTZ	5Me-BTZ	5Cl-BTZ	XTR	OH-BTZ
R_s (mL d ⁻¹)	257	582	614	550	519	510

Considering $R_s = A k_o$, with A the sampling surface area, R_s prediction as a function of water velocity can be undertaken:

$$\frac{1}{R_{s(in situ)}} = \frac{1}{R_{s,max}} + \frac{1}{A k_w}$$

Eq. 3.3-1

Values of k_w from Glanzmann et al were used to model the expected changes in $R_{s,in situ}$ with water velocity in the range 0.05-0.4 m d⁻¹. In this range of water velocity, the R_s for benzotriazole is expected to vary from a value <400 mL d⁻¹ for a water velocity of 0.05

m s^{-1} up to $> 500 \text{ mL d}^{-1}$ when the water velocity at the surface of the sampler reaches 0.4 m s^{-1} (Figure 3.3-4).

Figure 3.3-4: Modelling of the expected in-situ sampling rate R_s , for benzotriazole with a $R_{s,max} = 582 \text{ mL d}^{-1}$ for a POCIS device with a $5 \mu\text{m}$ stainless steel membrane and a sampling surface area of 40 cm^2 for water velocities in the range of 0.05 to 0.4 m s^{-1} . The blue dotted line is for visual effect only. The dotted orange line indicates $R_{s,max}$.

3.3.3 Full-scale calibration experiment

After spiking the water, concentrations in the test system were on average $0.066 \pm 0.07 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$ for atrazine (0.065 ng mL^{-1}), benzotriazole (0.073 ng mL^{-1}), 5-chlorobenzotriazole (0.062 ng mL^{-1}) and 5,6-dimethyl benzotriazole (0.064 ng mL^{-1}). There appeared to be high concentrations of 5Me-BTZ in the water before spiking but the concentrations in the spiked water were lower than this. The results for the OH-BT were also inconsistent and hence both analytes have not been included in the results, while the results are further investigated.

The water concentration had depleted by approximately 25% by day 4 of the experiment and a re-addition of chemicals was made to the water, which increased the average water concentration on day 5 to $0.085 \pm 0.03 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$ for the same four chemicals (Figure 3.3-5).

Figure 3.3-5: Average water concentrations \pm standard deviation ($n=2$) of benzotriazoles and atrazine in the water over the first 14 days of the laboratory calibration experiment. The black dashed line represents 80% of the average original measured spike concentration.

All chemicals of interest accumulated in the POCIS sampler with Affinisep's HLB disc. A simple numerical model taking into account the changes in contaminant concentration in water over time was used to optimise a compound-specific sampling rate R_s assuming linear uptake throughout the 7-day exposure (**Error! Reference source not found.**Figure 3.3-6). Optimisation of R_s was based on minimising the deviation between observed and predicted masses of chemical accumulated in the sampler after 1, 2, 4 and 7 days. In a second step, the model was adapted to take into account possible slowing down of the accumulation as a result of reaching pseudo-equilibrium (Table 3.3-5). Assuming linear uptake over the 7-day exposure period, sampling rate estimates were in the range of 137 and 232 mL d⁻¹ for 5Me-BTZ and BTZ to 643 mL d⁻¹ for XTR. The inclusion of a receiving phase-water distribution coefficient, K_d , generally improves the agreement between the model output and the observed accumulation. This is shown by the smaller RMSEs for the latter (Table 3.3-5). RMSE values decreased from values in the range of 0.22-0.31 to 0.11-0.21. Predicted R_s values were higher however and in the range of 267 to 865 mL d⁻¹. Modelled $\log K_d$ values (K_d , L kg⁻¹) were in the range of 3.34 to 4.34. These values are in line with values obtained earlier using batch experiments. This modelling indicates that for some compounds a deviation from linear uptake could be observed over 7 days.

In general, these sampling rates are high and higher than expected from stainless steel membrane calibration, particularly considering only half of the side of POCIS was exposed (20 instead of 40 cm² sampling surface). The water velocity at the surface of the samplers is ~ 29 cm s⁻¹. Considering the 5 cm-amplitude of the horizontal shaker set at 150 rpm, the velocity of the membrane in diffusion cell experiments is of the same order of magnitude (~ 25 cm s⁻¹). It could however be that the diffusion cell experiment underestimated the mass transfer across the stainless-steel membrane.

Figure 3.3-6: Measured and modelled masses of ATZ, BTZ, 5Cl-BTZ and XTR accumulated (m_{ACC} in ng sampler⁻¹) over seven days in the POCIS device with 20 cm² sampling surface, 5 μ m stainless-steel membrane and Affinisep's HLB disc. Modelled uptake shown here is based on optimising R_s and K_d . Note that the y-axis does not have the same scale for all plots.

Table 3.3-5: Modelled R_s and R_s and K_d values for device such as POCIS with a 20 cm² sampling surface and equipped with a 5 μ m stainless steel membrane and Affinisep's HLB disc.

	ATZ	BTZ	5Cl-BTZ	XTR
Linear uptake				
R_s (mL d ⁻¹)	625	232	642	643
RMSE	0.23	0.28	0.21	0.22
Non-linear uptake				
R_s (mL d ⁻¹)	854	408	759	865
logK _d (mL g ⁻¹)	4.15	3.59	4.34	4.18
RMSE	0.17	0.11	0.19	0.16

The use of the same stainless-steel membrane but with a different receiving phase (OASIS/Altantic™ HLB disc) resulted in sampling rates sensibly lower than those with Affinisep's HLB disc (Figure 3.3-7 and Table 3.3-6). Sampling rates were compound-specific and in the range 58-232 mL d⁻¹. As a result of these lower R_s values, this POCIS

version appeared to remain in the linear phase of uptake for 7 days (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Since sampling rates are different for the different receiving phases, this tends to indicate that the sorbent discs impact the sampling rates. As shown in Figure 3.3-8, sampling rates appear lower for compounds with lower affinity for the sorbent disc and this shows uptake is likely partly controlled by the receiving phase. The membrane, as originally thought from the diffusion cell experiment appears not to be solely controlling the sampling rate as expected from membrane calibration. The OASIS/Atlantic™ disc is relatively thick and compounds have to diffuse through that matrix before sorbing to the HLB sorbent distributed in the matrix. This process is most likely responsible for the lower sampling rates observed. The sampling rates obtained with this version of POCIS are in line with expectations but due to transfer within the receiving phase rather than transfer through the membrane.

Figure 3.3-7: Measured and modelled masses of ATZ, BTZ, 5CI-BTZ and XTR accumulated (m_{ACC} in $ng\ sampler^{-1}$) over 7 days in the POCIS device with $20\ cm^2$ sampling surface, $5\ \mu m$ stainless-steel membrane and OASIS/Atlantic™ HLB disc. Modelled uptake shown here is based on optimising R_s . Note that the y-axis does not have the same scale for all plots.

Table 3.3-6: Modelled R_s values for device such as POCIS with a 20 cm² sampling surface and equipped with a 5 μm stainless steel membrane and an OASIS/Atlantic™ HLB disc.

	ATZ	BTZ	5Cl-BTZ	XTR
Linear uptake				
R_s (mL d ⁻¹)	220	120	217	232
RMSE	0.075	0.084	0.1	0.063

Figure 3.3-8: Relationship between modelled R_s (mL d⁻¹) and $\log K_d$ (K_d , L kg⁻¹). Note the regression is presented a visual guide only.

4 Passive and active sampling tools PM substances in air matrices

4.1 Introduction

Active and passive air sampling are methods used to sample and airborne (gaseous and aerosol/particulate-bound) contaminants:

- Active air sampling involves using mechanical devices like a pump to actively draw air through a sorbent phase, tube and filters. These devices are calibrated to control the flow rate, allowing for measurement of contaminant concentrations in the volume of air sampled.

- Passive sampling relies on the passive transfer of chemicals present in air to in contact with a passive sampler receiving phase, such as a sorbent material. Contaminants are adsorbed or absorbed onto the sorbent phase over a period of time. These measurements are cost-effective and convenient for long-term monitoring.

The focus here is on active sampling with a view to estimate possible losses of PM substances to the air during sludge treatment processes at the University of the Aegean.

4.2 Active gas phase sampling

Active gas phase sampling was undertaken in the context of ZeroPM substances in order to assess the full mass balance of chemicals spiked in remediation experiments conducted at the University of the Aegean. Passive and active sampling has previously been undertaken to estimate air concentrations of PM substances in the gas and aerosol phases (Johannessen et al., 2022; Xue et al., 2017). Isolute® ABN cartridges were selected for this as a result of prior experience with air sampling with these as part of past screening projects on behalf of the Norwegian Environment Agency.

Commercially available ABN cartridges and custom made XAD resin cartridges were prepared for testing at NIVA. XAD resin (2 g) was placed in empty 6 mL SPE cartridges with a frit placed on top of them. Cartridges were conditioned through solvent rinsing (acetone, cyclohexane) and kept in aluminium foil until use. GF/F filters were placed in the cartridges in order to separate largest particles from the samples.

Testing of the two types of cartridges was conducted in the NIVA's building garage. Replicate cartridges of each type were connected with tubing to rotameters and then to a laboratory vacuum pump (Figure 4.2-1). Rotameters were set to 50 mL s⁻¹. The first sample was collected over 18 hours, resulting in an air volume sampled of 3.24 m³. The second sample had a volume 0.72 m³.

Figure 4.2-1: Testing of ABN SPE cartridges and XAD resin for the sampling of airborne benzotriazoles. GF/F filters were placed in front of the SPE cartridges.

Samples were stored wrapped in aluminium foil and placed in the freezer at -20 °C until extraction and analysis. The GF/F filters were removed prior to extracting cartridges. Cartridges including duplicate blank cartridges were placed onto an SPE extraction manifold and eluted with 2x 5 mL of methanol. Prior to elution, samples were spiked with internal standards for benzotriazole, triazine and PFAS compounds. Once eluted the 10 mL samples were reduced to 1 mL under a gentle flow of nitrogen. Filters were soaked in 2 mL of methanol and placed in ultrasonic bath (2x 15 min).

Cartridges prepared and used for sampling hydrothermal carbonisation gases were eluted in the same way and analysed for benzotriazoles.

4.2.1 Active air/gas sampling

Active air sampling making use of ABN SPE cartridges and XAD-2 resin cartridges and conducted in the garage at NIVA (Oslo) were analysed for atrazine and benzotriazoles. Results are shown in Table 4.2-1. Volumes of air sampled were 3.24 and 0.72 m³. None of the chemicals were found above limits of quantification in air of the garage. A more suitable test sampling site may be needed. An option is to conduct this testing in the air of one of Oslo's underground sewage treatment plants.

Table 4.2-1: Concentrations of PM substances in air of garage at Økernveien 94, 0579 Oslo measured with active sampling with ABN SPE cartridges or XAD-2 resin.

	ATZ	BTZ	5Me-BTZ	5Cl-BTZ	XTR	OH-BT
C _{air} * pg m ⁻³	<13	<28	<28	<80	<37	<2800
C _{air} ** pg m ⁻³	<55	<124	<122	<357	<163	<13000
*From 3.24 m ³ sampled volume						
**From 0.72 m ³ sampled volume						

5 Conclusions

The design and testing of a passive sampling strategy for PM substances has progressed substantially. Sorbent-water batch experiments and diffusion cell studies were conducted to attempt to identify suitable materials for the construction of a passive sampler targeting PM substances. A full-scale calibration experiment was conducted to measure sampling rates for two passive sampler configurations. The following can be concluded:

- Sorbent-water distribution coefficients for atrazine and benzotriazoles are sufficiently high for use in a passive sampler.
- Output of diffusion cell experiments with stainless steel membranes confirming the 5 µm pore size membrane is likely to reduce and control the uptake adequately.
- Sampling rates of the first passive sampler configuration (5 µm stainless steel membrane and Affinisep's HLB disc) are substantially higher than predicted from diffusion cell data. Since these are relatively high, they are likely to be

sensitive to water turbulence levels. As a result of high R_s , the exposure time window for integrative uptake appears to be relatively short.

- Sampling rates of the second passive sampler configuration (5 μm stainless steel membrane and OASIS/Atlantic™ HLB disc) are significantly lower than those obtained with the first sampler and in the expected range. Linear uptake is expected for a longer period of time for this version of POCIS.
- Mass transfer resistance in the matrix of the OASIS/Atlantic™ HLB disc appears to contribute significantly to control R_s .
- Active air/gas sampling was evaluated with two types of cartridges (ABN sorbent and XAD-2 resin). Testing was conducted with garage air as a possible source of benzotriazole. None of the benzotriazoles were found in garage air above limits of quantifications, with these below ng m^{-3} level for most compounds. This testing may be repeated in air more likely to contain these compounds as well as other PM substances. ABN sorbent cartridges were used for sampling gas during hydrothermal carbonisation experiments at the University of the Aegean as part of future work in ZeroPM.).

Some results are awaited and include (i) analysis of samplers and water samples from the calibration experiment for other PM substances, (ii) analysis of silicone membranes used for evaluating boundary layer conditions during diffusion cell experiments (this step helps clarify discrepancies observed above).

This is work in progress and some next steps are planned or identified:

1. Improving/optimising sampler design by using batch sorption, diffusion cell and full-scale calibration experiments to:
 - Test alternative membranes (thicker stainless-steel membrane; setting agarose gel in stainless steel pores)
 - Evaluate contribution of the receiving phase to mass transfer resistance into the sampler configuration
 - Increase the versatility of the sampler by casting alternative SPE sorbents into agarose gel to form a suitable receiving phase.
2. Using the calibration system to validate the final design(s) of passive sampler under different water velocities.
3. Collaborating with DVGW to deploy passive samplers in river water, groundwater well and at drinking treatment plant to:
 - Evaluate changes in PM substance concentrations from river water to drinking water at a location in Germany (Tasks 7.2 and 7.3)
 - Investigate PFAS removal in pilot scale ion exchange system
4. Collaborating with University of the Aegean to deploy passive samplers to evaluate PM substance remediation in pilot wastewater treatment plant system (Task 7.4).

6 Acknowledgements

We thank Dr Malcolm Reid, Dr Jan Thomas Rundberget and Dr Laura Röhler from NIVA for their analytical expertise and advice. Furthermore, we acknowledge the work conducted by Chiara Scapuzzi on nitrosamines.

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8 Appendix

UPLC-MS/MS parameters

LC parameters:

Instrument:	Acquity UPLC, Waters
Run time:	6 min
Mobile phase A:	0.05% formic acid in 5 mM ammonium formate
Mobile phase B:	Acetonitrile:methanol, 3:1
Flow rate:	0.5 mL/min
Column:	ACQUITY UPLC BEH C8 1.7 μ m
Column temp:	50 °C
Injection volume:	2 μ L

MS parameters:

Instrument:	Xevo TQ-S, Waters
Electro-spray ionisation:	positive mode

Table 0-1: Mobile phase gradient

Time (min)	A%	B%
0	97	3
0.5	95	5
3.5	70	30
4.5	30	70
4.6	0	100
5.8	0	100
5.9	95	5
6	95	5

Table 0-2: Target analytes analysed and their corresponding internal/surrogate standards, retention time, parent and daughter ions and limits of detection (LOD).

Analyte	Internal standard/ surrogate	Retention time (min)	Parent (m/z)	Daughter (m/z)	LOD (ng mL ⁻¹)
ATZ	d5-atrazine	4.95	216.0 216.0	104.0 174.0	0.01
BTZ	d6-5-methylbenzotriazole	2.73	120.1 120.1	65.0 92.0	0.03
5Me-BTZ	d6-5-methylbenzotriazole	3.61	134.1 134.1	77.0 79.0	0.03
5Cl-BTZ	d6-5-methylbenzotriazole	4.00	154.0 154.0	90.0 99.0	0.08
XTR	d6-5-methylbenzotriazole	4.26	148.0 148.0	77.0 93.0	0.04
OH-BT	d6-5-methylbenzotriazole	4.08	152.0 152.0	92.0 124.0	2.64

H2020 project Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances
EU Grant Agreement No. 101036756